

Antibacterial Activity of Emperor Scorpion (*Pandinus imperator*) Venom against Some Selected Bacteria

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13287122>

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Abstract: Antimicrobial peptides (AMPs) are essential components of the innate immune system that display potent antimicrobial activity against a wide range of microorganisms. Scorpion venoms, known for their diverse molecular compositions, have been identified as rich sources of AMPs. This study focused on the antimicrobial potential of Emperor Scorpion (*Pandinus imperator*) venom against selected bacteria isolated from drinking water sources. The physicochemical characteristics of the venom were analyzed, revealing a colorless, odorless, transparent liquid with a pH of 4.5 that dries easily at room temperature. The study involved the collection of 50 Emperor Scorpions, with venom extracted through electrical stimulation. The venom was purified and tested against bacterial isolates, including *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Acinetobacter baumannii*. Analytical Profile Index (API) kits confirmed bacterial identification. The results revealed concentration-dependent antibacterial activity, with the highest zone of inhibition at 11.5mm (100% concentration) against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values ranged from 25% to 50%, while minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) was determined at 75%. The venom's effectiveness was comparable to commercial antibiotics. Physicochemical analysis, bacterial identification, and antimicrobial assays collectively support the potential of Emperor Scorpion venom as a non-toxic antibacterial agent. This research contributes valuable insights for further exploration of scorpion venom in therapeutic applications and suggests avenues for scorpion farming, extraction expertise, and public awareness to maximize the benefits of this natural resource.

Key Words: Emperor Scorpion, *Pandinus imperator*, Scorpion Venom, Antimicrobial Peptides, Antibacterial Activity.

1 Introduction

Antimicrobial is a substance that kills or inhibits the growth of microorganisms such as bacteria, fungi, protozoan, and viruses (Enerijiofi and Isola, 2019; Ovuru, et al., 2023). The discovery of antimicrobials like penicillin and tetracycline paved the way for better health for millions around the world. Before 1941, the year where penicillin was discovered, there were no true cure for some diseases such as gonorrhoea (a venereal disease involving inflammatory discharge from the urethra or vagina), strep throat (a painful infection in the throat caused by group A streptococcus), or pneumonia (a lung infection in which the air sacs are filled with fluid) (Cosgrove et al., 2003). The resistance to antibiotics is a rising concern among health care professionals, driving the search for peptides with antimicrobial activities in plants, bacteria, and animals (Adesina

et al., 2013; Shaini et al., 2010; Enerijiofi and Isola, 2019). Antimicrobial peptides (AMPs) are key effector of the innate immune response of animals and show antimicrobial therapy potency (Yibao et al., 2009; Ramamoorthy, 2009). Most AMPs that display hydrophobic and cationic properties have a molecular mass below 25 to 30 kDa (Marsh et al., 2009). So far, more than 2,000 natural AMPs have been isolated, sequenced and submitted (Jupeng et al., 2021). Some natural antimicrobial peptides are being developed for use either as antibiotics for topical use in healthcare or as preservatives in the food industry. Apart from the extreme diversity in their primary and secondary structures, AMPs have in vitro effects on a wide spectrum of bacteria (Gram-negative and Gram-positive) and cells, including parasites, tumor cells, fungi and viruses (Bulet et al., 2004). AMPs have non-specific processes involved in the antimicrobial action. The unique property of an antimicrobial

peptide is its ability to interact selectively with bacterial lipid membrane and cause disruption. This property could decrease the likelihood of microbes acquiring resistance to AMPs. This could give AMPs a major advantage over conventional antibiotics, and in response, these peptides have been extensively investigated as potential antimicrobial agents (Harris et al., 2009; Thennarasu et al., 2010a, b; Ramamoorthy et al., 2010). Scorpions are particularly resistant to bacterial aggressions, and it is of interest to analyze the molecules responsible for this resistance (Sabatier et al., 1996). The scorpion venoms have three different groups of ingredients and peptides, based on their molecular mass with enzyme activity such as hyaluronidases, phospholipases, and sphingomyelinase (Chao et al., 2008). The second group contains mainly a peptide fraction with molecular mass around and lower than 10 kDa such as toxins and cytolytic compounds. The third group is composed of components such as ions, free amino acids, biogenic amines, neurotransmitters, acylpolyamines, heterocyclic compounds and alkaloids (Ma et al., 2010; Kuhn-Nentwig, 2003). Different antimicrobial peptides such as micropores have been identified from plants and animals (He et al., 2008; Zhao et al., 2009), BmKb1 and BmKn2 (Zeng et al., 2004), Hadrurin (Torres-Larios et al., 2000) and Mucroporin (Chao et al., 2008). Caerin is an antimicrobial peptide that was first found in amphibian, Australian green tree frog (Wong et al., 1997). Later different variants were isolated from a number of Australian frogs of the *Litoria* genus (Brian et al., 2000; Steinborner et al., 1998) and African frog (Gottler and Ramamoorthy, 2009). In recent years, caerin and caerin-like antimicrobial peptides were been found in scorpions such as *Mesobuthus lupus* and *Mesobuthus martensii* (Luo et al., 2005). Antibacterial activity of caerin on Gram-positive and negative bacteria has been shown with only small variation in their minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values (Boland and Separovic, 2006; Chia et al., 2011).

The venom or antimicrobial peptides found in scorpion has shown a broad-spectrum activity against a wide range of pathogenic microorganisms. Viral, bacterial, fungal and parasitic infections ranging from malaria, hepatitis C, meningitis, tetanus, and many nosocomial infections, etc have been treated successfully with scorpion venom. Scorpion venom

is also used for treatment of non-communicable and neurological disease such as stroke, rheumatism, diabetes, cancer, brain tumor, human neuroblastoma cells etc (Attarde and Pandit, 2016; El-Bitar et al., 2015; Petricerich et al., 2013). The emperor scorpion (*Pandinus imperator*) and several additional venom peptides had been characterized as antibacterial peptides with a broad-spectrum of bacterial targets against even the antibiotic-resistant strains (Baradaran et al., 20112).

The purpose of this study was to determine the possibility of using The Emperor Scorpion (*Pandinus imperator*) venom as an alternative to conventional antibacterial agent against some bacterial isolates.

2 Methodology

2.1 Study Area

Gwagwalada is one of the six area councils of the Federal Capital Territory of Nigeria. Gwagwalada is also the name of the main town in the Local Government Area, which has an area of 1,043 km² and a population of 157,770 as of the 2006 census. It is located at an elevation of 210 meters above sea level. Its coordinates are 8°56'29" N and 7°05'31" E in DMS (Degree Minutes Seconds) or 8.94139 and 7.09194 in decimal degrees. Its Universal Transverse Mercator position is KQ98 and its Joint Operation Graphics reference is NC32-13 (Wikipedia, 2016).

2.2 Media and Preparation

All media used were prepared according to the manufacturer's standard preparation procedures.

2.3 Sample Collection

In the Zoology Department of the Faculty of Science at the University of Abuja, fifty Emperor Scorpions (*Pandinus imperator*) were selected for venom collection. The venoms were harvested using the electrical stimulation technique outlined by Ozkan and Filazi in 2004. A series of regular currents were applied to shock the scorpions until the venom was ejected. For this purpose, the scorpions were immersed in a saline solution for better electrical conduction and shocked with electrodes using a simple 12-volt battery. The venom droplets were collected in sterile test tubes, with part of the venom stored in ice and used within 30 minutes, while the rest was frozen until further use. The venom was recovered using distilled water and centrifuged at

10,000 g. The supernatant was freeze-dried and stored at -20°C until use. All venom collected was passed through a membrane filter.

2.4 Collection of Test Organisms

Drinking water samples, each totaling 20 ml, were collected from various sources of drinking water supply across the University of Abuja, including the main site, mini campus, and staff quarters. These samples were transported to the Microbiology Laboratory at the University of Abuja for culturing, isolation, and identification of specific test bacteria.

2.5 Preparation of Samples

2.5.1 Preparation of The Emperor Scorpion (*Pandinus imperator*) Venom

The venom of *Pandinus imperator* was collected and measured in percentage since the venom is in liquid state. Raw venom represents 100%, while 50%, 25%, and 12.5% were diluted with 50%, 75%, and 87.5% of appropriate neutral diluents (sterile water) respectively, and also at concentrations of 10, 20, 30, and 40 mg/ml.

2.5.2 Preparation of Test Organisms

The samples collected were taken to the laboratory in a sterile plastic container. Using the serial dilution method, bacteria from the drinking water samples were cultured on an enrichment medium, incubated, and plated on MacConkey agar at 37°C for 24 hours. Suspected colonies were further sub-cultured on selective media (CHROM agar, Eosin methylene blue (EMB), and Cetrimide agar). Colonies were identified based on their color: red, metallic green sheen, and blue-green/yellow-green. A single colony was picked, screened, and identified based on the Analytical Profile Index (API). The organism was sub-cultured on selective media and confirmed using standard biochemical techniques (Cheesbrough, 1998).

2.6 Antibacterial Activity of The Emperor Scorpion (*Pandinus imperator*) Venom (Peptides)

Antimicrobial sensitivity tests of the isolates were performed using the standard agar well diffusion method described by Bauer et al. (1996). The venom was tested at different concentrations (12.5%, 25%, 50%, and 100%) and (10, 20, 30, and 40 mg/ml)

to determine antibacterial activity by measuring the zones of inhibition.

2.7 Determination of Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC)

The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) was determined by preparing various concentrations (12.5%, 25%, 50%, and 100%) and (10, 20, 30, and 40 mg/ml) of the venom using the dilution method. Test tubes were set up with 2 ml of nutrient broth, with control tubes including venom control, organism control, and negative control. A 0.2 ml suspension of the test organisms was added to the test tubes. The preparation was incubated at 37°C for 24 hours, after which turbidity or clearness was observed. The least concentration with no turbidity was noted as the MIC value.

2.8 Determination of Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC)

The minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) was determined from the broth dilution resulting from MIC tubes by sub-culturing to the surface of freshly prepared nutrient agar plates using a sterile inoculating loop as described by Vollekova et al. (2001) and Usman et al. (2007). Test tubes showing no microbial growth after 24 hours of incubation were sub-cultured on nutrient agar plates. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours and observed for growth. The plates with the lowest concentration of the venom showing no bacterial growth were noted as the MBC.

2.9 Comparing the Effects of Emperor Scorpion Venom with Commercial Antibiotics

The results were compared with standard antibiotics. Inhibition effects were measured in terms of the zone of inhibition.

2.10 Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistics were used to analyze the data, including simple percentages and standard deviation of the mean. Microsoft Excel was used for statistical significance, and ANOVA was performed to determine if there were any statistically significant differences between the venoms and isolates. Differences in survival were considered significant when $P \leq 0.05$.

3 Results

3.1 Physical Characteristics of *Pandinus Imperator* Venom

The result of the physico-chemical characteristics of *Pandinus Imperator* venom is shown in Table 1. The venom was observed to be colorless, odorless, and a transparent liquid which dries easily at room temperature.

Table 1: Physical characteristics of *Pandinus Imperator* Venom

Colour	Odour	Form	pH	Room Temperature (28°C)
Colourless	Odourless	Transparent Liquid	4.5	Dried up easily

3.2 Analytical Profile Index (API-20E)

The result of the Analytical Profile Index of the bacterial identification of isolates shows the different bacteria isolated from the three water sources studied were *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *A. baumannii* (Table ??).

The result for the mean \pm SD inhibition zone of diameter of *Pandinus Imperator* venom against organisms isolated from University of Abuja drinking water at different concentrations of 25%, 50%, 75%, and 100% respectively is shown in Table 2. To interpret the results of the zones of inhibition, the antibacterial and inhibitory effect of the venom was considered at the concentration of 30 mg/ml as compared to that of chloramphenicol (30 μ g), a standard antibiotic. When interpreted using the CLSI, 2004 guide, a zone of chloramphenicol (30 μ g) 18 is sensitive, 12 is resistant, while 13-17 is intermediate.

The mean \pm SD of inhibition zone of ciprofloxacin against isolated organisms at different concentrations

Table 2: Zone Diameter of Inhibition (mm) of *Pandinus Imperator* Venom against organisms isolated from University of Abuja Drinking Water

Microorganisms	Zone Diameter of Inhibition (mm)			
	25	50	75	100
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	6.1 \pm 0.0	7.2 \pm 0.0	9.0 \pm 0.0	10.0 \pm 0.0
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	5.7 \pm 0.0	7.0 \pm 0.0	9.0 \pm 0.0	11.5 \pm 0.0
<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>	3.0 \pm 0.0	4.7 \pm 0.0	6.0 \pm 0.0	8.2 \pm 0.0

of 62.5 mg/ml, 125 mg/ml, 250 mg/ml, and 500 mg/ml is shown in Table 3.

3.3 Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) of *Pandinus Imperator* Venom

The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of *Pandinus Imperator* venom on isolated test organisms is shown in Table 4. This is the lowest concentration of the venom required to inhibit the growth of the organisms.

3.4 Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC) of *Pandinus Imperator* Venom

The minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) of *Pandinus Imperator* venom on isolated test organisms is shown in Table 5. This is the lowest concentration of the venom required to kill the organisms.

The MBC obtained in the study was 75%, indicating that the venom was effective against the isolated test organisms.

4 Discussion

This research was carried out to determine the antibacterial activities of *Pandinus imperator* venom against some selected bacteria.

Table 1 shows the physiochemical characteristics of the venom. According to this table, the venom is odorless, colorless, and a transparent liquid with a pH of 4.5 that dries up easily at room temperature.

Table ?? presents the Analytical Profile Index (API) results for selected bacteria obtained from water samples at the University of Abuja.

Table 2 displays the zone diameter of inhibition for different concentrations of *Pandinus imperator* venom against isolated organisms. The lowest zone of inhibition is 3 mm at 25% against *Acinetobacter baumannii*, while the highest is 11.5 mm at 100% against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*.

Table 3: Zone Diameter of Inhibition (mm) of Ciprofloxacin against isolated organisms

Microorganisms	Zone Diameter of Inhibition (mm)			
	62.5	125	250	500
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	26	31	36	38
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	26	27	34	35
<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>	23	25	28	31

Table 4: Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) of *Pandinus Imperator* Venom on isolated test organisms

Microorganisms	MIC (mm)			
	25	50	75	100
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	+	-MBC	-	-
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	+	-MBC	-	-
<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>	+	+	-MBC	-

Key: + = Clear (No growth), - = Turbid (Growth)

Table 5: Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC) of *Pandinus Imperator* Venom on isolated test organisms

Microorganisms	MBC (mm)			
	25	50	75	100
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	+	-MBC	-	-
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	+	-MBC	-	-
<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i>	+	+	-MBC	-

Key: + = Bacterial growth, - = No bacterial growth

Table 3 shows the zone diameter of inhibition for different concentrations of commercial antibiotics against isolated organisms. The lowest zone of inhibition is 23 mm at 62.5 mg/ml against *Acinetobacter baumannii*, while the highest is 38 mm at 500 mg/ml against *Escherichia coli*.

Table 4 provides the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of Pandinus imperator venom against isolated test organisms at different concentrations. The MIC for *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* is 25%, while for *Acinetobacter baumannii* it is 50%.

Table 5 shows the minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) of Pandinus imperator venom against isolated test organisms at different concentrations. The MBC for *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* is 50%, while for *Acinetobacter baumannii* it is 75%.

All the antibacterial activities, MIC, and MBC support the findings of Ahmed et al. (2012), Baradaran et al. (2012), Cao et al. (2012), Nie et al. (2012), Zhao et al. (2009), Carballar-Lejarazú et al. (2008), Gawade (2007), Lee et al. (2004), Reddy et al. (2004), and Reddy et al. (2003), among others.

The action of antimicrobial peptides toward bacterial membranes is initiated by electrostatic interactions with negatively charged components of membranes, such as strong interactions with lipopolysaccharides in the outer membrane of gram-negative bacteria and acidic phospholipids in the outer cell wall of gram-positive bacteria. After the initial attachment, antimicrobial peptides aggregate within membranes, leading to membrane destruction achieved through channel (pore) formation (Guo et al., 2013).

5 Conclusion

From this research work, it can be concluded or deduced that Venom of Pandinus imperator called Emperor Scorpion found in West Africa is an antibacterial agent that is non-toxic to animals, the scorpion venom has the same potency and can both be safely used as a therapeutic agent. **Conflict of interest**

All authors declare that there is no conflict of interest. The study was conducted impartially and without bias.

6 ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I would like to express my heartfelt gratitude to the Almighty God, to whom all praise and worship belong. My sincere appreciation goes to my Parent, Late Pastor Oladapo Peter Dahunsi and Dr Mrs Taiwo Olayinka Dahunsi. Special appreciation also to my wife Aisha Ejura Dahunsi for her encouragement.

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